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БИОМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

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EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF REBAMIPID IN THE TREATMENT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA

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ANNOTATION

Recently, functional diseases of the gastrointestinal tract are increasingly attracting the attention of specialists. According to numerous epidemiological studies, various functional disorders of the digestive system suffer up to 50-60% of the population. The issue of optimization of approaches to the treatment of these categories of patients remains extremely relevant and topical. The aim of our study was to investigate the efficacy of rebamipid in the treatment of functional dyspepsia in 50 patients. The results of the study showed that the inclusion of rebamipid in the complex therapy of functional dyspepsia leads to rapid relief of pain syndrome and other dyspeptic symptoms, as well as to the improvement of patients' quality of life.

Key words: functional dyspepsia, treatment, gastroprotectors, rebamipid.

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ОЦЕНКА ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ РЕБАМИПИДА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ДИСПЕПСИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В последнее время функциональные заболевания желудочно-кишечного тракта все чаще привлекают к себе внимание специалистов. По данным многочисленных эпидемиологических исследований, различными функциональными расстройствами пищеварительной системы страдают до 50-60% населения. Вопрос оптимизации подходов к лечению данных категорий больных остается крайне актуальным и злободневным. Целью нашего исследования явилось изучение эффективности применения ребамипида в лечении функциональной диспепсии у 50 пациентов. Результаты исследования показали, что включение в комплексную терапию функциональной диспепсии ребамипида приводит к быстрому купированию болевого синдрома и других диспепсических симптомов, а также к улучшению качества жизни пациентов.

Ключевые слова: функциональная диспепсия, лечение, гастропротекторы, ребамипид.

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FUNKSIONAL DISPEPSIYANI DAVOLASHDA REBAMIPIDNING SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH

ANNOTATSIYA

So'nggi paytlarda oshqozon-ichak traktining funktsional kasalliklari mutaxassislar e'tiborini tobora ko'proq jalb qilmoqda. Ko'pgina epidemiologik tadqiqotlarga ko'ra, ovqat hazm qilish tizimining turli funktsional buzilishlari 50-60% aholida kuzatiladi. Ushbu toifa bemorlarni davolashga yondashuvlarni optimallashtirish masalasi juda dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Tadqiqotimizning maqsadi 50ta bemorda funktsional dispepsiyani davolashda rebamipidning samaradorligini o'rganish edi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, rebamipidni funktsional dispepsiya uchun kompleks terapiyaga kiritish og'riq va boshqa dispeptik simptomlarni tezda bartaraf etishga, shuningdek, bemorlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilashga olib keladi.

Kalit so'zlar: funktsional dispepsiya, davolash, gastroprotektorlar, rebamipid.

Funksional dispepsiya (FD) oshqozon-ichak traktining keng tarqalgan kasalliklaridan biri bo'lib, dunyo aholisining deyarli 1/5 ida kuzatiladi. FD deganda bemorda oxirgi 3 oy davomida kuzatilgan epigastral soxada og'riq va kuyish hissi, ovqatdan keyin epigastral soxada to'liqlik hissi va erta to'yinganlik kabi buzilishlar majmuasi tushuniladi [1]. FD ambulatoriya amaliyotida dispepsiyaning barcha holatlarining taxminan 10-15% ni tashkil qiladi.

FD ning patofiziologiyasi to'liq o'rganilmagan. FD patogenezini gastroduodenal soxaning multifaktor buzilishi va oshqozon, o'n ikki barmoqli ichak shilliq qavati retseptorlari apparatining visseral yuqori sezuvchanligini o'z ichiga oladi. Birinchisining mexanizmlarida oshqozon tubining joylashishining buzilishi va oshqozon antrumidan ovqatni evakuatsiya qilishning sekinlashishi alohida o'rin tutadi [2]. Shu bilan birga, me'daning motor funksiyasi normal bo'lgan ba'zi bemorlarda funksional dispepsiya belgilari ham bo'lishi mumkin, bu, ehtimol, oshqozonning visseral yuqori sezuvchanligi, asosan kengayish bilan bog'liq. Visseral yuqori sezuvchanlik funksional dispepsiya bilan og'riqan bemorlarning 34-65 foizida aniqlanadi va dispepsiya belgilarining og'irligi bilan bog'liq.

Rim IV mezonlariga ko'ra, FD uchta variantga bo'linadi: postprandial distress sindromi (PDS), epigastral og'riq sindromi (EOS) va PDS va POS o'rtasidagi aralash variant. [3]. FD turiga qarab davolashning quyidagi bosqichlari ajratiladi: birinchi darajali terapiya antisekretor dorilar yoki prokinetiklar, agar ular samarasiz bo'lsa, ikkinchi darajali dorilar - antidepressantlar va kerak bo'lganda psixoterapevt bilan maslahatlashish kereak [4]. FD bilan og'riqan bemorlarni davolash uchun taklif qilinadigan ko'plab dori terapiyasi variantlarining mavjudligi ma'lum darajada shifokorlarning FD bilan kasallangan bemorlarni davolash natijalaridan noroziligini ko'rsatadi [5]. Bu, ehtimol, nafaqat dispepsiya belgilarining patogenezini yetarli darajada bilmaslik, balki umuman FD sindromi patogenezini, shuningdek, FD variantlarini farqlashda tez-tez yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklar bilan bog'liq. Bu turli xil populyatsiyalar, shu jumladan etnik guruhlardagi bemorlar tomonidan dispepsiyaning ko'plab belgilarini talqin qilish sezilarli darajada farq qilishi bilan izohlanadi.

Tadqiqot maqsadi: funksional dispepsiyani davolashda rebamipid gastroprotektorining samaradorligini o'rganish .

Tadqiqot materiallari va usullari: 25 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha bo'lgan 50 nafar bemorlar ambulator sharoitda tekshirildi. Dispepsiya belgilari bilan gastroenterologga murojaat qilgan (epigastral sohada og'riq va kuyish hissi, ovqatdan keyin epigastral sohada to'liqlik hissi). Ularning 29 nafari ayol va 21 nafari erkak edi. O'rtacha yoshi 41,2 edi $\pm 7,5$ yil. Ushbu alomatlar so'nggi 3-4 oy ichida bemorlarda kuzatilgan. Guruhlar uchun tanlov mezonlari: endoskopik tekshiruv vaqtida oshqozon shilliq qavatida eroziv va yarali o'zgarishlarning yo'qligi, *Helicobacter pylori* infeksiyasining yo'qligi, shuningdek, quyidagi alomatlardan kamida ikkitasi: epigastral og'riq, epigastral sohada kuyish hissi, ovqatdan keyin to'liqlik hissi. Tadqiqotga dispepsiya belgilarining og'irligiga ta'sir qilishi mumkin bo'lgan og'ir somatik patologiyasi bo'lgan bemorlar kiritilmagan.

Tadqiqotda oddiy randomizatsiya usuli bilan bo'lingan bemorlarning 2 guruhi ishtirok etdi. O'rganilayotgan guruhlardagi bemorlarni tasodifiy ajratish yoshi va jinsini, FD paydo bo'lish sabablarini, klinik ko'rinishini, laboratoriya va instrumental tadqiqot usullari natijalarini hisobga olgan holda amalga oshirildi. Birinchi guruhdagi bemorlar - 25 kishi 30 kun davomida kuniga 40 mg pantoprazol qabul qildi. Ikkinchi guruhdagi bemorlar - 25 kishi, 40 mg pantoprazol bilan rebamipid (Rebagit, PRO.MED.CS Praha, Chexiya) 300 mg/kun (kuniga 3 marta 100 mg) qabul qildi.

Barcha bemorlar keng qamrovli klinik, laboratoriya va instrumental tekshiruvdan o'tkazildi. Terapiyaning samaradorligi og'riq intensivligini o'lchash uchun 10 ballli vizual analog shkala (VASH) va hayot sifatini baholash uchun SF-36 so'rovnomasi yordamida baholandi. Barcha guruhlardagi bemorlarga butun davolanish davrida spirtli ichimliklar, tamaki va achchiq ovqatlardan voz kechish tavsiya etildi.

Ma'lumotlar o'rtacha \pm standart og'ish sifatida taqdim etildi. Statistik ahamiyatlilik Student mezonlar yordamida baholandi. Muhimlik mezoni $p < 0,05$.

Natijalar va muhokama:

Bemorlarda FDning eng ko‘p uchraydigan alomati epigastral og‘riq edi. Og‘riq zo‘rayishi dinamikasi bemorlarning birinchi tashrifida va davolanishning 7, 14 va 30-kunlaridagi tashriflarida baholandi. Davolashdan oldin birinchi guruh bemorlarida epigastral og‘riq 21 (84%) bemorda, epigastral sohada yonish hissi - 23 (92%) bemorda qayd etilgan. Ikkinchi guruhda klinik belgilar nisbati birinchi guruh ma’lumotlaridan sezilarli darajada farq qilmadi: epigastral og‘riqlarga shikoyatlari 22 ta (88%) bemorda, epigastral sohada kuyish hissi – 20ta (80%) bemor tomonidan qayd etilgan. Shu bilan birga, terapiyaning 7-kunida guruhlarda sezilarli farqlar kuzatilmadi, terapiyaning 30-kuniga kelib, pantoprazol va rebamipid bilan kombinatsiyalangan terapiyani olgan guruhda epigastral og‘riqning intensivligi sezilarli darajada past edi ($p < 0,01$). Shuni ta’kidlash kerakki, rebamipidni pantoprazol bilan birgalikda qabul qilgan ikkinchi guruhda pantoprazol monoterapiyasini olgan birinchi guruhga nisbatan 7-kundan boshlab sezilarli yaxshilanish kuzatildi ($p < 0,02$).

14 kunlik davolash kursidan so‘ng, birinchi guruhda ham, ikkinchi guruhda ham kasallikning asosiy belgilari (epigastral sohada og‘riq va kuyish hissi, ovqatdan keyin to‘liqlik hissi) bartaraf etilishi kuzatildi. Shu bilan birga, 1-jadvaldan ko‘rinib turibdiki, pantoprazol bilan antisekretor terapiya olgan bemorlarga nisbatan rebamipid bilan kombinatsiyalangan terapiya o‘tkazilgan bemorlarda asosiy klinik simptomlarni yo‘qolish vaqti ancha oldinroq bo‘lgan.

1-jadval.

Nazorat guruhlardagi bemorlarda asosiy klinik simptomlarning davolanishning 14-kunida yo‘qolishi dinamikasi.

Bemorlar guruhlari	Bemorlar soni	Epigastral og‘riq	Epigastriumda yonish hissi	Ovqatdan keyin to‘yish hissi
Pantoprazol (birinchi guruh)	25	7,3±0,27	6,3±0,31	5,8±0,31
Pantoprazol +rebamipid (ikkinchi guruh)	25	4,8±0,15*	4,3±0,29*	3,7±0,22*

* - $p < 0,05$ da taqqoslash guruhi ma’lumotlariga nisbatan o‘zgarishlarning ishonchliligi.

Terapiyaning 30-kuniga kelib, birinchi va ikkinchi guruhlardagi dispeptik sindromning to‘liq yengilligi 95% gacha bemorlarda kuzatilgan va ikki guruhdagi statistik jihatdan sezilarli farq yo‘qolgan ($p < 0,07$).

Bemorlarning hayot sifati (HS) davolashdan oldin va 30-kunida SF-36 so‘rovnomalari yordamida baholandi. Har bir shkala bo‘yicha ballar 0 dan 100 gacha baholandi, 100 - to‘liq salomatlikni anglatadi va barcha shkalalar ikkita ko‘rsatkichni tashkil qiladi: aqliy va jismoniy farovonlik. Natijalar 8 ta shkala bo‘yicha ballar sifatida taqdim etilgan bo‘lib, yuqori ball HS ning yuqori darajasini ko‘rsatadigan tarzda tuzilgan.

Bizning tadqiqotimizda rebamipidni pantoprazol bilan birgalikda qabul qilgan bemorlarda og‘riq sezilarli darajada pasaygani qayd etildi. Bundan tashqari, kombinatsiyalangan terapiyani olgan bemorlar SF-36 so‘rovnomasining emotsional roli va ruhiy salomatlik shkalasi bo‘yicha davolanish oxirida yuqori ball ko‘rsatdi. Shuningdek, kombinatsiyalangan terapiya fonida bemorlarning ikkinchi guruhida umumiy salomatlik va hayot faoliyati shkalasi bo‘yicha yuqori ball qayd etildi.

Qiyosiy tahlil shuni ko‘rsatdiki, ikkinchi guruhdagi bemorlarda kasallikning klinik barqarorlashuvi ancha oldinroq va ko‘p sodir bo‘lgan. Belgilangan o‘zgarishlar, ehtimol, rebamipidning pantoprazolning antisekretor ta'sirini kuchaytirishi va shu sababli, xlorid kislotaning oshqozon va o‘n ikki barmoqli ichak shilliq qavatiga ta'sir qilish vaqtini qisqartirishi va bemorda simptomlarni yengillashtirishi bilan bog‘liq. Bundan tashqari, prostaglandin E2 stimulyatsiyasi tufayli oshqozon sekretsiyasini kuchli bostirish, oshqozon antral qismida oziq-ovqat gidroksillanish vaqtini qisqartirish orqali oshqozondan evakuatsiya boshlanishini tezlashtirishi mumkin va oshqozon kengayishidan kelib chiqadigan belgilarning intensivligini va chastotasini kamaytirishga yordam beradi [6]. Bundan tashqari, rebamipid oshqozon shilliq qavatini qon bilan ta'minlashni yaxshilashga

yordam beradi, uning baryer funksiyasini faollashtiradi, oshqozonning ishqoriy sekretsiyasini faollashtiradi, oshqozon epiteliy hujayralarining ko'payishi va metabolizmini kuchaytiradi, shilliq qavatni gidroksil radikallardan tozalaydi [7] va lipidlarni peroksidlanish jarayonini kamaytiradi.

Xulosa: Shunday qilib, rebamipidni funksional dispepsiyaning kompleks terapiyasiga kiritish og'riq va boshqa dispeptik simptomlarni tezda bartaraf etishga, shuningdek, bemorlarning hayot sifatini yaxshilashga olib keladi.

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